

RESEARCH OF ALISHER NAVOI DEVONS IN THE FIELD OF TEXTUAL STUDIES

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Annotation. This article deals with the “Ilk devon” (First Devonian) compiled by the admirers of Alisher Navoi, the official devons ordered by the poet himself: the devons “Badoyi’ ul-bidoya” and “Navadir un-nihoya”, their manuscript copies, issues of study in the second half of the 20th century.

Keywords: “Ilk devon” (First Devonian), “Badoyi’ ul-bidoya”, “Navadir un-nihoya”, question of periodization, genre structure, manuscript copies.

Alisher Navoi left himself a very large and rich lyrical legacy in terms of volume. The basis of this lyrical treasure is the “Khazoyin ul-maoniy” (Treasure of meanings), which contains about 45 thousand verses of Uzbek language, and the “Devoni Foni”, which contains more than 12 thousand verses of Persian-Tajik language, the “Sittai karabiyya”, which consists of 6 philosophical oaths in Persian-Tajik language, as well as the “Fusuli arba” oaths dedicated to the image of the seasons. In addition, considering in the poet's epics (lyrical preface, lyrical retreat and lyrical wife), as well as the independent verse, individual, ruboi, poetic masterpieces of the continent and other genres, which are found in the composition of other prose works, we are once again convinced of how immense the poet's lyrics are.

“For Navoi, poetry was the main School of gaining skill in the field of creativity, no one left under any circumstances of the poet's life, was a constant favorite and convenient creative activity. The artist went to his great epic works through lyricism, and his impressions of life were systematically embodied, first of all, in lyricism. It is never possible to imagine the work of a thinker without lyrics, at the same time to separate his lyrics from Epic and scientific creativity”[1]. The role of poetry lovers in the composition of the poet devons has become incomparable. In 1465-1466 ad (870 ah), the first devotional Office of the poet came into being. Although this devon is referred to as an informal devon, Alisher is an invaluable example of Navoi lyricism. The famous calligrapher Sultan Ali Mashhadi copied Devon with a letter from Nasta'liq. Unfortunately, while the name of the muse who decorated this Devon with patterns is still not known to science, Devon was also not given a special name by the poet. Devonian includes poems written before 1466 by the poet. Even because

the date of writing the poems in it is relatively clear, it has a “high value as a certain imaginative source of the poet's creativity and translator holi during adolescence and boyhood” [2].

Two copies of the fan-made Devon are known to the people of science to date, the first being a manuscript copied by the Sultanali Mashhadi in 870/1565-66. Today, this copy of Devon is stored in the city of St. Petersburg, in the National Library of Russia under the inventory number Dorn 564. A second copy is kept in Kazan, in the Scientific Library of Kazan State University under inventory number 1742. This variant of Devon was copied by Mahmud the scribe in 976/1567068. All the poems in the work were later included in the lyrical cull “Khazoyin ul-maaniyy”.

The poet, at the suggestion of his friend Sultan Husayn Boyqaro, gives order to the official First Dynasty between the 1470s and 1480s, naming it “Badoyi’ ul - bidoya” (“genesis of artistry”). Devon was a great reality in the literary life of the 15th century, in which the contemporary creator was much different from his devons. The need to give a place even to the debocha part in the Devonian arrangement in Uzbek classical devonism began from this Devonian in the manner of creative experience, according to the study of Egyptologists. In addition, Alisher Navoi contributes to the reform and perfection of the eastern Devonian. In Devon, after debocha, he arranges ghazals, and then works of a different genre, in the Arabic alphabet, strictly in order, relying on his last letter in radifi or rhyme. In addition, the great poet places special importance on the subject and ideological orientation of the poems. Copies of Devon in the poet's time (1480, 1482 and 1486) are in the Bibliothèque Nationale de Paris (1480, inv. No. 746), at the British Museum (1482-y).

The first volume of Alisher Navoi's twenty-volume “collection of Perfect Works” is composed by the poet's office “Badoyi’ ul-bidoya”. This edition was edited by Özr FA H.S. A manuscript copy of Devon at the Suleymanov manuscript Institute (inv. № 216) was taken as a basis, compared with photonusches of other manuscripts that remained. When preparing the first roof of the collection, Sh.Sharipov, M.Rahmatullaeva and M.The work of the ziyoviddinovas was unparalleled .

This edition of "Badoyi' ul-bidoya", containing works of eleven genres of poetry, comprises Ghazal – 777, mustazad – 3, mukhammas – 5, musaddas – 2, Tarje'band – 3, Kontinental – 46, ruboi – 85, luqz – 10, problem – 52, chicken – 10 and fard – 53 in Devon. The total number of poems in this Devon is 1046, giving it an unofficial” first devon " - F.Y) part of the poems are included.

The second Devonian, ordered by Alisher Navoi, was known as “Navadir un-nihoya” (“the vile ignorant”), dating from between 1480 and 1487. A manuscript copy copied by Khattat Abdujamil at Herat in 1487 is today in the Institute of Oriental

Studies named after O‘zr FA Abu Raikhan Beruniy (inv. No. 11675, base copy) is stored. The manuscript consists of 149 sheets and consists of 840 ghazals.

Another relatively more complete manuscript copy of the “Navodir un-nihoya” Devan was copied by Sultan Ali Mashhadi in Hirot at the Institute of Oriental Studies named after O‘zr FA Abu Raykhon Beruniy (inv. No. 1995). On the basis of this manuscript copy, the “Navadir un-nihoya” office was published in 1987, in preparation of this edition, the existing two manuscript copies were compared, and this edition, consisting of 862 poems, was published by M.Rahmatullaeva and G.Performed by the ahrorovas [3].

In a copy copied by the Sultan Mashhadi of Devon, esa (inv. №1995) there are 693 poems in the cross section of genres: Ghazal – 628, mustazad – 3, Tarji'band – 3, Continent – 5, ruboi – 46, luqz – 1, problem – 6 and chicken – 1.

The composition of these genres is comparable to the earlier Devonian ones, with the majority of Devonian dialects (63 out of 65) being contained in “Badoyi’ ul-bidoya”. This is a surprising case. Because” ul jam'u orzidin other (“Badoyi’ ul-bidoya”) than har taqr bila har nav’ abyotkim, pronounced erdiyu har nav’ ghazaliyotkim, gathered and melted (referring to” Navadir un-nihoya“”) by the author in the” Khazoyin ul-maoniy " debocha, most of the poems of different genres in Devon should be new. From the studies of the scholars involved in the poet's lyricism, we observe that the poet's poetry from the period up to the “Khazoyin ul-maoniy” was renewed as he passed from Devon to Devon . Questions that have not been solved as above are bisyor. This suggests that serious research should be done on the poet's lyrics, in particular on his devons. In addition, the poet also wrote a debocha for the” Navadir un-nihoya " Devo, and the author, in the lyrical cull of “Khazoyin ul-maaniyy”, gives the following thought quotes:"... in my second devonim, “Navadir un-nihoya” is famous, rabt-he ordered, and in debochasida commentary bila aizzayi as'hobu ajillayi told him in the services of ahbab". But this debocha, which the author points out in poetic cullyat, does not appear in the manuscripts that have come down to us, nor in the modern editions of Devon. This gives rise to the idea that a perfect Devon copy has not yet been found, and has spurred further research.Bu kabi tadqiqotlar XXI asrda ham davom etib, filologiya fanlari doktori Aftondil Erkinov tomonidan A.Navoiy devonlarining jahon qo‘lyozma fondlarida saqlanayotgan nusxalarini tadqiq etishi natijasida, shoir muxlislari tomonidan tuzilgan yana bir devon qo‘lyozmasi topildi va 2012-yilda fanga ma’lum qilindi [4]. Olim tomonidan mazkur qo‘lyozma ustida jiddiy tadqiqot olib borilib, fikr-mulohazalarini qator maqolalar orqali e’lon qilib kelmoqda [5].

From the point of view of the scope and content of the research carried out, the study of the lyrics of Alisher Navoi in the Uzbek navoism of the 20th century was carried out on two main principles, the first direction was carried out on a textual study of the lyrical heritage of the Great Creator.

Originally a lyrical legacy from the time of the poet's life, the manuscripts of his devons were spread over different countries. Historian Khondamir (1475-1535 / 37) writes that in the 15th century, a huge number of copies of Navoi's works were taken by trade figures, scientists and cultural figures from India, the Middle East and arab countries . Today, the manuscripts are held in a number of manuscript holdings in Asia, Europe, Africa, and America. The poet's devons reached Europe from 1625, with A. D. from Oxford University, England. There is information that the Nawab has adopted a thermo Devon, which is currently kept with the number 283.

In the development of the field of preparation, publication and popularization of the scientific-critical text of the poet's lyrics in the second half of the 20th century, the navoiologist scholar H.Suleymanov's services were great. By the textualist, in 1957-58, he traveled through the cities of the former Union, where there are oriental manuscripts (St. Petersburg, Dushanbe, Tbilisi, Baku, Almaty, Ashgabat, Frunze, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Fergana and others), adding with personal libraries of all universities, Academy foundations, scientific institutions, Tashkent funds, informs that he accounted for more than 1200 manuscripts of the poet's works [6]. The introduction by the scientist to the composition of the critical text of “Khazoyin ul-maoniy” and the almost complete publication of his first devotional “Wonder us-khotar” and his second devotional “Navadir ush-Shabab” in the new Uzbek Alphabet in 1959 on the basis of this critical text indicates a new level of Uzbek navoism in this field. In 1960, the remaining two devons were also published. As a result of the hard work of the scientist, “Xazoyin ul-maoniy”, “Xamsa”, “Ilk devon”, “Sittayi zaruriya”, “Fusuli arb’a” were presented to readers. In Uzbek genealogy, he was one of the first to make the first Devonian of the Nawab. Suleymanov prepared for publication. The scholar prints a facsimile (photo) copy of Devon (manuscript copied 1466) under the title “Ilk devon” in 1968 . This “Ilk devon” contains 391 ghazals, 1 mustazad, 1 mukhammas and 41 ruboi, all of which comprise 434 poems. In genealogy, the work is a reliable source for studying the early stages of the lyrical legacy of the great thinker.

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